

Spectrophotometric Identification and Determination of Antioxidants in Vulcanised Rubber

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Recently Hilton¹ described spectrophotometric methods for identification and determination of the amine and phenol type antioxidants of rubber. The method is based on the well-known colour reaction of the amines and phenols with diazonium compounds and subsequent determination of absorption in a spectrophotometer. Hilton¹ observed that depending on the nature of the antioxidants (amine or phenol), either acidic or alkaline pH is to be used in order to have stable colour formation. This is the basis of the present work which reports such determinations in the case of some amine and phenol type antioxidants, not investigated by Hilton.

Experiments were conducted with (a) original antioxidants in ethanolic solution (except in the case of Nonox CI, which was dissolved in acetone) and (b) with antioxidants extracted from vulcanised rubber.

(a). A 0.5% solution (0.1 ml) of the antioxidants was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask and was mixed with 1 ml of the coupling agent [diazotised *p*-nitroaniline, prepared by mixing equal volumes of *p*-nitroaniline (0.005*M*) in HCl and sodium nitrite (0.0062*M*) in water]. In the cases of HFN and AN, colour developed immediately and the absorbance was measured after making the volume to 50 ml with ethanol. In the cases of WSP, EX, NS, NSN, EXN, SP, CC, and CI, the colour developed after adding 2.5 ml of *N*/2-NaOH after which the volume was made to 50 ml and the absorbance was measured with a spectrophotometer. The wave lengths at maximum absorption together with the trade name and chemical composition of the antioxidants are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Antioxidant.	λ_{max} .	Visual colour.	Chemical composition of the antioxidant.
Nonox EX	545 m μ	Red	A phenol condensate,
" WSP	590	Blue	A phenol derivative.
" EXN	530	Red	A phenol condensate.
" NSN	530	Red	Phenol-aldehyde amine
" NS	530	Red	Do
" SP	530	Violet	A mixture of styrenated phenols.
" CC	520	Red	A phenolic sulphide.
" CI	520	Red	<i>sym</i> -Di- β -naphthyl- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine.
" HFN	530	Red	A blend of arylamines.
" AN	530	Red	Phenyl- α -naphthylamine.

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1. *Rubber Age*, 1958, 84, 283; *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 383.

(b). The rubber mix, used to ascertain the suitability of the method for determination of the antioxidants in vulcanised rubber and also to study the interference, if any, from common rubber compounding ingredients, was the same as reported in previous work². This was mixed with appropriate quantities of different antioxidants to give about 0.5% antioxidants on rubber and vulcanised for 30 mins. at 150°. The powdered sample (1g.) was extracted with acetone for 16 hours. The extract was evaporated to dryness on a water bath and the residue was dissolved in about 20 ml of ethanol to which were added 3 drops of liquor ammonia and 3 drops of 20% strontium chloride solution in order to precipitate the fatty materials. The solution was kept overnight. The supernatant liquid was filtered, washed with little ethanol, and the volume made to 50 ml in a volumetric flask. This solution (5 ml) was treated as in (a) for the development of colour and measurement of absorbance.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra of various antioxidants.

FIG. 2. Absorption spectra of various antioxidants.

FIG. 3. Variation of absorbance against concentration.

TABLE II

Antioxidant.		% Added.	% Found.		% Error.	
Nonox	EX	0.703	0.685	0.696	-2.5	-0.99
"	WSP	0.508	Colour development unsatisfactory			
"	EXN	0.481	0.476	0.462	-1.0	-3.7
"	NSN	0.513	0.498	0.494	-2.9	-3.6
"	NS	0.606	0.592	0.583	-2.3	-3.7
"	SP	0.443	0.435	0.435	-1.8	-1.8
"	CC	0.503	0.489	0.515	-2.7	+1.1
"	CI	0.546	0.530	0.525	-2.9	-3.8
"	HFN	0.461	..	0.450	..	-0.4
"	AN	0.650	0.650	0.679	-1.5	+2.8

Table II shows the difference of percentage added and found, the quantity found being obtained from Figs. 1 and 2, following the conventional methods of absorption spectrophotometry. The method has been found not suitable for Nonox WSP, when extracted from vulcanised rubber. Identification in most cases has also been found difficult since wave length at maximum absorption lies very close to one another (Table I).

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